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SCHOOL LEARNING ENVIRONMENT VARIABLES AS PREDICTORS OF BIOLOGY STUDENTS' ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT IN SENIOR SECONDARY SCHOOLS OF TARABA STATE, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the school learning environment variables as predictors of biology students' academic achievement in senior secondary schools of Taraba State, Nigeria. Six objectives, six research questions and six null hypotheses guided the study. The study adopted the correlational research design. The population was 11,837 SSS III Biology students. The sample of the study was 400 SSS III biology students drawn from the entire using population. A total of 16 senior secondary schools were selected from four education zones using multi-stage sampling techniques. Two instruments were used for data collection namely: School Learning Environment Variables Questionnaire (SLEVQ) and Biology Students' Academic Achievement (BSAA). Cronbach Alpha was used to obtain the reliability coefficient of School Learning Environment Variables Questionnaire and Kuder-Richardson 21 formula (KR-21) was used to compute the reliability coefficient of Terminal Biology Students' Academic Achievement (BSAA). The reliability coefficient of 0.82 was obtained for School Learning Environment Variables Questionnaire and 0.80 was obtained for Biology Students' Academic Achievement. Instrument was subjected to face validation. Descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions while, the null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance using simple linear regression and multiple linear regression an. The analyses findings of the study revealed that there is positive significant relationship between school learning environment variables combined (class size, home environment, students-teacher relationship, biology laboratory facilities and school location) and biology students' academic achievement in senior secondary schools of Taraba state (P-value 0.00). It was concluded that class size, teacher-students relationship, home environment, biology laboratory facilities and school location make a positive significant prediction on biology students' academic achievement in senior secondary schools in Taraba state. Therefore, it was recommended that Government, parents, teachers, individual and school principals should ensure that school learning environment variables: are given proper attention for better academic achievement of students in Taraba State senior secondary schools.

Keywords: School, Learning, Environment, Variable, Academic Achievement

INTRODUCTION

Education is the bedrock and an indispensable tool for Societal development and socio-economic development of the society. With a conducive learning environment, countries in the world see education as a good investment for national development because it is expected to produce the required quantity and quality of human resources for socio-economic growth (Mosha, 2012). A good system of education in any country should be effective in two ways: First, the quantitative

level is used to ensure access to education and quality in the distribution and allocation of resources to various segments of the society. Second, on the qualitative level to ensure that the country produces the skills needed for rapid social and economic development (Babalola & David, 2011). Therefore, these dual ways are important for meaningful development in the society that may foster the students' academic achievement, particularly in science subjects such as Biology, Chemistry, Mathematics, and Physics for improving science education.

Biology as a natural science subject deals with contents from microscopic organisms to the biosphere that encompassing the earth's surface and all living things (Okwo & Tartiyus, 2004). Biology today is viewed as a standard subject of instruction at all levels of our educational systems, from pre-primary to tertiary level because of its fundamental characteristics and importance. It is the only core science subject at Senior School Certificate Examination (SSCE), whose study is very relevant to man's successful living (Akindele, 2009). Araoye (2009) opined that exposure to biology education offers the learners a wide range of relevance to all aspects of life. The idea behind biology as a course of study is to acquire knowledge, career, skills, method, highly motivated, professional, and effective teachers of biology who will be able to develop in students, an appreciation and understanding of biological processes and principles (Okenyi, 2012).

Secondary schools in Taraba state have been observed and reported as not living up to expectations in delivering quality education expected of the school system. A lot of problems seem to be bedeviling the secondary school students' academic achievement among the biology students. Study of Rowe (2012) has shown a high enrolment and low academic achievement trend of students in internal and external biology examinations WACE between 2016 and 2020. Chief Examiner reported 68.6% failure in biology in 2014/2017. According to Rowe (2012) despite the popularity and simplicity of biology as a subject, the failure rate has remained persistent. Rowe, further pointed out that 82.1% failure in West Africa Senior School Certificate Examination in (WACE) between 2016 and 2020 in Taraba state. The poor academic achievement may be caused by poor school learning environment variables. Rowe (2012) identified school learning environment problems like wrong school location, large class size, lack of Biology laboratory facilities, unconducive home environment and negative attitude of teachers toward students. These problems have posed great challenges to the teaching and learning process and also may hinder the biology students' academic achievement in senior secondary schools in Taraba State. It is generally believed that if the school learning environment variables are unconducive, biology students in senior secondary schools will be taught well and there would be a risk of proper academic achievement. The problem of the study is: what may be prediction the school learning environment variables with academic achievement Taraba state? Can school learning environment variables in Taraba state improve biology students' academic achievement in the state, since literature has revealed that the biology students' academic achievement is poor in the state.

PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

The main purpose of this study is to investigate the school learning environment variables as predictors of biology students' academic achievement in senior secondary schools of Taraba state. The specific objectives of the study are to determine whether:

1. Class size predicts biology students' academic achievement in senior secondary schools of Taraba State.
2. Home environment predicts biology students' academic achievement in senior secondary schools of Taraba State.
3. Teacher-student relationships predict biology students' academic achievement in senior secondary schools of Taraba State.

4. Laboratory facilities predict biology students' academic achievement in senior secondary schools of Taraba State.
5. School location predicts biology students' academic achievement in senior secondary school of Taraba State.
6. School learning environment variables (class size, home environment, teacher-student's relationship, laboratory facilities, and school location) collectively predict biology students' academic achievement in senior secondary schools of Taraba State.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The study seeks to answer the following research questions to guide the study:

1. What is the level of biology students' class size in senior secondary school in Taraba State?
2. What is the level of biology students' home environment in senior secondary school in Taraba State?
3. What is the level of teacher-student relationships in senior secondary school in Taraba State?
4. What is the level of biology students' laboratory facilities in senior secondary school in Taraba State?
5. What is the level of biology students' school location in senior secondary school in Taraba State?

HYPOTHESES

The following null hypotheses were formulated and were tested at a 0.05 level of significance to guide the study:

- H₀₁:** There is no statistical significant relationship between class size and Biology students' academic achievement.
- H₀₂:** There is no statistical significant relationship between home environment and Biology students' academic achievement.
- H₀₃:** There is no statistical significant relationship between teacher-student relationships and Biology students' academic achievement.
- H₀₄:** There is no statistical significant relationship between laboratory facilities and Biology students' academic achievement.
- H₀₅:** There is no statistical significant relationship between school location and Biology students' academic achievement.
- H₀₆:** There is no statistical significant relationship between school learning environment variables (class size, home environment, teacher-student's relationship, laboratory facilities, and school location) and Biology students' academic achievement.

METHODOLOGY

This chapter describes the methods used in carrying out the study under the following sub-headings; research design, area of the study, the population of the study, sample and sampling technique, instrument for data collection, validation of the instrument, reliability of the instrument, procedure for data collection and method of data analysis.

This study adopted the correlational research design. The correlational research design is a design where a researcher seeks to determine the relationship between two or more variables. The purpose of using this design agreed with Yabo (2007) which stated that predictive research is a search for relationships between variables measured at one point and the variables measured at another point in time, meaning that such a study indicates the direction and magnitude of the relationship between the variables. This study described the relationship that exists between school learning environment sub variables and biology students' academic achievement.

This study adopted the correlational survey research design. The area of this study is Taraba State, Nigeria. The population of this study comprises 11,837 Senior Secondary School in Taraba State. According to Post-Primary School

Management Board of Taraba State statistics of students (PPSMB, 2020), there are 5211 males and 6626 females with major tribes of Jukun, Igbo, Yoruba and Hausa. The sample was drawn from the entire population of 11,837 Senior Secondary School Students across the ten education zones of Taraba State, Nigeria. Taro Yamane's (1973) formula with a 95% level of confidence which is recommended for large population was used to calculate the sample from the population. Two instruments were used for data collection. The School Learning Environment Variables Structure Questionnaire (SLEVSQ) and Terminal Examination Score of Biology Students' Academic Achievement Questionnaire (TESQBSAA) contained in a proforma. The scale used in answering the research questions were VHL5, HL4, ML3, LL2 and VLL1. This is five points scale. The instrument of this study was subjected to face validity. The items in questionnaires were face validated by four lecturers. Three lecturers were from the Department of Environmental and Life Sciences Education. Two of the three lecturers have biology education background, one with curriculum and instruction background. One lecturer from the Department of Physical Sciences Education with mathematics background all of them are in Modibbo Adama University (MAU), Yola.

The reliability of the instrument was determined through a pilot test. For pilot testing, 30 respondents from Government Day Senior Secondary Schools Donga, Taraba State which is not part of the main study area were used. Cronbach Alpha was used after collecting data to compute the internal constituency of the School Learning Environment Variables Structure Questionnaire (SLEVSQ) while, Kuder-Richardson 21 formula (KR-21) was used to compute the internal constituency of the Terminal Examination Scores of Biology Students' Academic Achievement Questionnaire. The internal consistency value of was 0.82. School Learning Environment Variables while the internal consistency terminal of biology students' academic achievement (TESQBSAA) was 0.80. An introductory letter from the Department of Environmental and Life Sciences Education, Faculty of Education, Modibbo Adama University, Yola, was obtained for the researchers. The researchers personally monitored the administration of the instrument's by visiting the selected schools in eight-local government areas of the four education zones within four weeks. After filling the questionnaires by respondents from each school, the research assistants assisted the researcher in collecting back the completed copies of the two instruments after one week of distribution.

Descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation were used to answer research questions while simple linear regression statistical analysis and multiple linear regression statistical analysis were used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. Using real limit of numbers, any item with mean of 3.50 and above was regarded as high level, moderate level 2.50- 3.49 and less than 2.50 - 3.49 was low level.

RESULTS

Research Questions One. What is the level of biology students' class size in senior secondary schools in Taraba state?

Table 1. Descriptive statistics of the level of biology students' class size in senior secondary school in Taraba state.

S/N	Items	n = 400	Mean	Std. Dev	Remark
1.	Indicate the level to which the small class sizes give students time to develop their skills in biology practical		4.00	0.82	High Level
2.	Indicate the level to which the students learn better in large class sizes at biology practical.		3.47	1.01	Moderate Level
3.	Indicate the level to which teachers give students class exercise in small class size than large class size.		3.71	1.26	High Level

4.	Indicate the level to which the use of audiovisual aids in large class would make the lessons more interesting	4.01	1.18	High Level
5.	Indicate the level to which class of 35 students involve in biology practical enhance their academic achievement.	4.25	1.12	High Level
6.	Indicate the level to which small class size enhances students' academic achievement.	3.85	1.42	High Level
7.	Indicate the level to which managing large class size allows students to learn effectively without disturbing one another.	3.89	1.11	High Level
8.	Indicate the level to which the small class size does not give students comfort to learn well during biology class.	3.02	1.43	Moderate Level
Grand Mean		3.79		High Level

The result of analysis presented in Table 1 indicates that all the items except items 2 and 8 have mean score of 3.50 and above which is the cut-off mark of high level, this implies that, the biology students' class size in senior secondary school of Taraba state has high level result of learning.

Research Questions Two. What is the level of the biology students' home environment in senior secondary school in Taraba state?

Table 2. Descriptive statistics of the level of biology students' home environment in senior secondary school in Taraba state.

S/N	Items	n= 400	Mean	Std. Dev	Remark
9.	Indicate the level to which students in conducive home environment study well after the school hours		4.02	1.59	High Level
10.	Indicate the level to which home environment is not favourable to student who study after school hour.		3.21	1.54	Moderate Level
11.	Indicate the level to which parents' involvement in students learning at home give them better achievement		3.69	1.27	High Level
12.	Indicate the level to which the students' study extra or ahead of the teacher at home give them better academic achievement in school.		4.70	0.46	Very High Level
13.	Indicate the level to which the students who involve in much domestic work at home do not have time to study ahead of the teacher		4.27	1.11	High Level
14.	Indicate the level to which the students' academic achievement in senior secondary schools is determined by home environment		3.85	1.42	High Level
15.	Indicate the level to which good parenting behavior enhance students academic achievement.				High Level
16.	Indicate the level to which students' reading habits are influential features of the home learning environment.		3.84	1.11	Moderate Level

Grand Mean	3.91	High Level
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The result of analysis presented in Table 2 shows that all the items except items 10 and 16 have mean score 3.50 which is the cut-off mark high level and the grand mean of 3.91, this implies that, the Biology student's' home environment in senior secondary school in Taraba state is of high learning result.

Research Questions Three. What is the level of teacher-student relationships in senior secondary school in Taraba state?
Table 3. Descriptive statistics of the level of teacher-student relationships in senior secondary school in Taraba state

S/N	Items	n= 400	Mean	Std. Dev	Remark
17.	Indicate the level to which teachers create time for students to ask questions in the biology practical class		4.27	1.22	High Level
18.	Simplicity of teachers with the students during class affect their academic achievement.		4.04	1.25	High Level
19.	Indicate the level to which teachers' relationship with students give them room to achieve better in school.		3.78	1.20	High Level
20.	Indicate the level to which students are free to approach their teacher when they need academic help.		4.50	0.92	Very High Level
21.	Indicate the level to which students feel discouraged when their teachers are harsh to them		4.07	0.83	High Level
22.	Indicate the level to which the good relationship among teachers students in the class enhance students' academic achievement.		4.29	1.16	High Level
23.	Indicate the level to which teacher good relationship with students improve their study habit		3.67	1.39	High Level
24.	Indicate the level to which the teachers habit of bully enhance students' academic achievement.		3.48	1.29	Moderate Level
Grand Mean			4.15		High Level

Table 3 result presented above revealed that all the items except item 24 have mean score of 3.50 and above which is the cut-off mark and the grand mean of 4.15, this implies that, the teacher-student relationships in senior secondary school in Taraba state is high.

Research Questions Four. What is the level of biology students’ laboratory facilities in senior secondary school in Taraba state?

Table 4. Descriptive statistics of the level of biology students’ laboratory facilities in senior secondary school in Taraba state.

S/N	Items	n=400	Mean	Std. Dev	Remark
25.	Indicate the level to which biology teachers use laboratory for practical class.		4.05	1.25	High Level
26.	Indicate the level to which biology laboratory has facilities for student’s practical.		3.98	1.39	High Level
27.	Indicate the level to which biology laboratory facilities are utilized effectively.		4.70	0.45	Very High Level
28.	Indicate the level to which laboratory facilities can enhances students’ academic achievement.		4.31	1.15	High Level
29.	Students who study biology with practical do better than those without practical class.		3.80	1.01	High Level
30.	The used of laboratory facilities during class make students understand the lessons easier		4.14	1.33	High Level
31.	Indicate the level to which the use of laboratory facilities help teacher to delivery lesson easier.		4.24	1.26	High Level
32.	Indicate the level to which the use of laboratory facilities gives students logical thinking		3.98	1.31	High Level
Grand Mean			3.98		High Level

Table 4 result presented above indicates that all the items have mean score of 3.50 and above which is the cut-off mark high level and the grand mean of 3.98, this implies that, the biology laboratory facilities in senior secondary school in Taraba state is high.

Research Questions Five. What is the level of biology students’ school location in senior secondary school in Taraba state?

Table 5. Descriptive statistics of the level of biology students’ school location in senior secondary school in Taraba state.

S/N	Items	n=400	Mean	Std. Dev	Remark
33.	Indicate the level to which a good location of school help students to attend biology class regularly		4.40	0.92	High Level
34.	Indicate the level to which the location of the school make positive impact to students.		3.91	1.15	High Level
35.	Indicate the level to which location of school in noisy area causes poor academic achievement among biology students.		4.15	1.10	High Level
36.	Indicate the level to which students learn better in a quiet environment.		4.39	0.94	High Level
37.	Indicate the level to which the students in urban area learn better than students in a rural area during biology practical		3.49	1.28	Moderate Level

38. Indicate the level to which good setting of school enhances students' academic achievement	4.05	1.25	High Level
39. Poor academic achievement of biology students is attributed to wrong school location	3.53	1.51	High Level
40. Indicate the level to which an environment mismatch affected students' academic achievement positively.	3.84	1.17	High Level
Grand Mean	4.10		High Level

Table 5 result presented above postulated that all the items except item 37 have mean score of 3.50 and above which is the cut-off mark for high level and the grand mean of 4.10, this implies that, the biology students' school location in senior secondary school in Taraba state is high.

Hypotheses Testing

H0₁: There is no statistical significant relationship between class size and Biology students' academic achievement.

Table 7a: Model Summary of Regression Analysis between Class Size and Biology Students' Academic Achievement

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.728 ^a	.530	.529	2.880

Table 7a revealed the model summary between class size and Biology students' academic achievement. The data summarized in the table shows an R-value of 0.728, an R² value of 0.530, and an adjusted R² value of 0.529. The R² value of 0.530 indicates that 53% of the total variation in biology students' academic achievement can be accounted for by class size. The remaining 47% could be attributed to other variables not factored in the model. This result shows that the class size makes positive prediction on students' Biology academic achievement. Table 7b shows the significance of the regression model.

Table 7b: Summary of Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) of Regression between Class Size and Biology Students' Academic Achievement

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	3720.61	1	3720.61	448.56	.000 ^b
	Residual	3301.24	398	8.295		
	Total	7021.84	399			

Significant; p < 0.05

Table 7b indicated how well the regression equation fits the data; the table indicates that the regression model predicts the dependent variable significantly. This implies that (F (1, 398) = 448.56, p = 0.00 < 0.05). This affirms that the regression model is a good fit for the data. Table 7c is the coefficients table which provides the necessary information to predict biology students' academic achievement from class size, as well as determine whether biology students' academic achievement contributes significantly to the model.

Table 7c: Summary of Regression Coefficients between Class Size and Biology Students' Academic Achievement

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
		B	Std. Error	Beta	T	Sig.
1	(Constant)	3.464	1.307		2.65	.008
	Class Size	0.908	0.043	0.73	21.18	.000

Significant; $p < 0.05$

The relative contribution of class size to the observed variance in the criterion variable (students' academic achievement) is indicated by the R and R² values. The result in Table 7c further emphasizes the results in the preceding tables which shows that there is a statistically significant relationship between class size and biology students' academic achievement ($\beta = 0.73$, $t = 21.18$, $p = 0.00 < 0.05$). Hence, the null hypothesis of no significant prediction is hereby rejected.

H0: There is no statistical significant relationship between home environment and Biology students' academic achievement.

Table 8a: Model Summary of Regression Analysis between Home Environment and Biology Students' Academic Achievement

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.573 ^a	.328	.327	3.443

Table 8a postulate the model summary between home environment and biology students' academic achievement. The data summarized in the table shows an R-value of 0.573, an R² value of 0.328, and an adjusted R² value of 0.327. The R² value of 0.328 indicates that 32.8% of the total variation in students' biology academic achievement can be accounted for by the home environment. The remaining 67.2% could be attributed to other variables not factored in the model. This result shows that the home environment predicts biology students' academic achievement. Table 8b shows the significance of the regression model.

Table 8b: Summary of Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) of Regression between Home Environment and Biology Students' Academic Achievement

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	2304.98	1	2304.98	194.49	.000 ^b
	Residual	4716.86	398	11.85		
	Total	7021.84	399			

Significant; $p < 0.05$

Table 8b revealed how well the regression equation fits the data; the table indicates that the regression model predicts the dependent variable significantly. This implies that ($F(1, 398) = 194.49$, $p = 0.00 < 0.05$). This affirms that the regression model is a good fit for the data. Table 8c is the coefficients table which provides the necessary information to predict biology students' academic achievement from home environment, as well as determine whether Biology students' academic achievement contributes significantly to the model.

Table 8c: Summary of Regression Coefficients between Home Environment and Biology Students' Academic Achievement

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
		B	Std. Error	Beta	T	Sig.
1	(Constant)	12.15	1.36		8.92	.000
	Home Environment	0.60	0.04	0.57	13.95	.000

Significant; $p < 0.05$

The relative contribution of the home environment to the observed variance in the criterion variable (students' academic achievement) is indicated by the R and R² values. The result in Table 8c further emphasizes the results in the preceding tables which shows that there is a significant relationship between home environment and biology students' academic achievement ($\beta = 0.57, t = 13.95, p = 0.00 < 0.05$). Hence, the null hypothesis of no significant prediction is hereby rejected.

H0₃: There is no statistical significant relationship between teacher-student relationships and Biology students' academic achievement.

Table 9a: Model Summary of Regression Analysis between Teacher-student relationship and Biology Students' Academic Achievement

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.572 ^a	.328	.326	3.445

Table 9a indicated the model summary between the Teacher-student relationship and biology students' academic achievement. The data summarized in the table shows an R-value of 0.572, an R² value of 0.328, and an adjusted R² value of 0.326. The R² value of 0.328 indicates that 32.8% of the total variation in biology students' academic achievement can be accounted for by the Teacher-student relationship. The remaining 67.2% could be attributed to other variables not factored in the model. This result shows that the Teacher-student relationship predicts biology students' academic achievement. Table 9b shows the significance of the regression model.

Table 9b: Summary of Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) of Regression between Teacher-student relationship and Biology Students' Academic Achievement

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	2299.69	1	2299.69	193.83	.000 ^b
	Residual	4722.15	398	11.87		
	Total	7021.84	399			

Significant; $p < 0.05$

Table 9b postulated how well the regression equation fits the data; the table indicates that the regression model predicts the dependent variable significantly. This implies that ($F(1, 398) = 193.83, p = 0.00 < 0.05$). This affirms that the regression model is a good fit for the data. Table 9c is the coefficients table which provides the necessary information to predict biology students' academic achievement from the Teacher-student relationship, as well as determine whether Biology students' academic achievement contributes significantly to the model.

Table 9c: Summary of Regression Coefficients between Teacher-student relationship and Biology Students’ Academic Achievement

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
		B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.
1	(Constant)	10.689	1.47		7.28	.000
	Teacher-student relationship	0.612	0.04	0.57	13.92	.000

Significant; $p < 0.05$

The relative contribution of the Teacher-student relationship to the observed variance in the criterion variable (students’ academic achievement) is indicated by the R and R² values. The result in Table 9c further emphasizes the results in the preceding tables which shows that there is significant relationship between Teacher-student relationship and biology students’ academic achievement ($\beta = 0.57, t = 13.92, p = 0.00 < 0.05$). Hence, the null hypothesis of no significant prediction is hereby rejected.

H0₄: There is no statistical significant relationship between laboratory facilities and Biology students’ academic achievement.

Table 10a: Model Summary of Regression Analysis between School laboratory facilities and Biology Students’ Academic Achievement

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.428 ^a	.183	.181	3.797

Table 10a indicated the model summary between School laboratory facilities and biology students’ academic achievement. The data summarized in the table shows an R-value of 0.428, an R² value of 0.183, and an adjusted R² value of 0.181. The R² value of 0.183 indicates that 18.3% of the total variation in biology students’ academic achievement can be accounted for by School laboratory facilities. The remaining 81.7% could be attributed to other variables not factored in the model. This result shows that the School laboratory facilities predict biology students’ academic achievement. Table 10b shows the significance of the regression model.

Table 10b: Summary of Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) of Regression between School laboratory facilities and Biology Students’ Academic Achievement

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	1283.57	1	1283.57	89.03	.000 ^b
	Residual	5738.27	398	14.42		
	Total	7021.84	399			

Significant; $p < 0.05$

Table 10b shows how well the regression equation fits the data; the table indicates that the regression model predicts the dependent variable significantly. This implies that ($F(1, 398) = 89.03, p = 0.00 < 0.05$). This affirms that the regression model is a good fit for the data. Table 10c is the **coefficients** table which provides the necessary information to predict biology students’ academic achievement from School laboratory facilities, as well as determine whether biology students’ academic achievement contributes significantly to the model.

Table 10c: Summary of Regression Coefficients between School laboratory facilities and Biology Students' Academic Achievement

Model			Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients			
			B	Std. Error	Beta	T	Sig.	
1	(Constant)		18.06	1.38			13.06	.000
	School laboratory facilities	laboratory	0.41	0.04	0.43		9.44	.000

Significant; $p < 0.05$

The relative contribution of School laboratory facilities to the observed variance in the criterion variable (students' academic achievement) is indicated by the R and R² values. The result in Table 10c further emphasizes the results in the preceding tables which shows that there is a significant relationship between School laboratory facilities and biology students' academic achievement ($\beta = 0.43$, $t = 9.44$, $p = 0.00 < 0.05$). Hence, the null hypothesis of no significant prediction is hereby rejected.

H0s: There is no statistical significant relationship between school location and Biology students' academic achievement.

Table 11a: Model Summary of Regression Analysis between School location and Biology Students' Academic Achievement

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.187 ^a	.035	.032	4.127

Table 11a revealed the model summary between School location and biology students' academic achievement. The data summarized in the table shows an R-value of 0.187, an R² value of 0.035, and an adjusted R² value of 0.032. The R² value 0.035 indicates that 3.5% of the total variation in biology students' academic achievement can be accounted for by School location. The remaining 96.5% could be attributed to other variables not factored in the model. This result shows that the School location predicts biology students' academic achievement. Table 11b shows the significance of the regression model.

Table 11b: Summary of Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) of Regression between School location and Biology Students' Academic Achievement

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	244.32	1	244.32	14.35	.000 ^b
	Residual	6777.52	398	17.03		
	Total	7021.84	399			

Significant; $p < 0.05$

Table 11b posited how well the regression equation fits the data; the table indicates that the regression model predicts the dependent variable significantly. This implies that ($F(1, 398) = 14.35$, $p = 0.00 < 0.05$). This affirms that the regression model is a good fit for the data. Table 11c is the coefficients table which provides the necessary information to predict biology students' academic achievement from School location, as well as determine whether biology students' academic achievement contributes significantly to the model.

Table 11c: Summary of Regression Coefficients between School location and Biology Students’ Academic Achievement

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
		B	Std. Error	Beta	T	Sig.
1	(Constant)	23.22	2.06		11.27	.000
	School location	0.24	0.06	0.19	3.79	.000

Significant; $p < 0.05$

The relative contribution of School location to the observed variance in the criterion variable (students’ academic achievement) is indicated by the R and R² values. The result in Table 11c further emphasizes the results in the preceding tables which shows that there is significant relationship between School location and biology students’ academic achievement ($\beta = 0.19$, $t = 3.79$, $p = 0.00 < 0.05$). Hence, the null hypothesis of no significant prediction is hereby rejected.

H0₆: School learning environment variables (class size, home environment, teacher-student relationship, laboratory facilities, and school location) do not significantly predict biology students’ academic achievement.

Table 12a: Model Summary of Regression Analysis between School Learning Environment variables and Biology students’ Academic Achievement

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.849 ^a	.721	.718	2.228

Data in Table 12a shows that predictor variable (School learning environment variables combine) taken against the criterion variable (biology students’ academic achievement) yielded following values: $R = 0.849$, $R^2 = 0.721$ and adjusted $R^2 = 0.718$. The R² value of 0.721 implies that only 72.1% of the variance in biology students’ academic achievement can be determined by School learning environment variables. In order words, the R² value, which is relatively low suggests that School learning environment variables combined (i.e., class size, home environment, teacher-student relationship, laboratory facilities, and school location), predict biology students’ academic achievement. Table 12b provides an explicit detail of this regression equation.

Table 12b: Summary of ANOVA of Regression between School Learning Environment variables and Biology students’ Academic Achievement

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	5066.18	5	1013.24	204.13	.000 ^b
	Residual	1955.66	394	4.96		
	Total	7021.84	399			

Significant; $p < 0.05$

Table 12b indicates whether the regression equation is a good fit for the data. From the analysis, it could be seen that School learning environment variables significantly predict biology students’ academic achievement ($F(5, 394) = 204.13$, $p = 0.00 < 0.05$). The shows that the regression equation is a good fit for the data.

Table 12c: Summary of Regression Coefficients between School Learning Environment variables and Biology students’ Academic Achievement

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
		B	Std. Error	Beta	T	Sig.
1	(Constant)	-9.115	1.659		-5.493	.000
	Class Size	.691	.037	.554	18.549	.000
	Home Environment	.143	.043	.136	3.323	.001
	Teachers Students Relationship	.307	.049	.287	6.306	.000
	Laboratory Facilities	.182	.030	.192	6.116	.000
	School Location	-.039	.043	-.031	-.915	.361

Significant; $p < 0.05$

The composite correlation coefficients between predictors (School learning environment variables combine) and biology students’ academic achievement are significant. Testing the predictive effect of individual predictor variable on biology students’ academic achievement reveals the following results: Class size ($\beta = 0.554$, $t = 18.549$, $p = 0.000$), Home Environment ($\beta = 0.136$, $t = 3.323$, $p = 0.001$), Teachers’ students relationship ($\beta = 0.287$, $t = 6.306$, $p = 0.000$), School laboratory facilities ($\beta = 0.192$, $t = 6.116$, $p = 0.000$) and School location ($\beta = -0.031$, $t = -0.915$, $p = 0.361$). It could be seen that the p values for the four predictor School learning environment variables combine are lesser than 0.05, except school location, hence the findings show that there is significant relationship between School learning environment variables combine and biology students’ academic achievement. Thus, the null hypothesis of no significant prediction is hereby rejected

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

This study investigated school learning environment variables as predictors of biology students’ academic achievement in the senior secondary school of Taraba state, Nigeria. The study determined the level of class size, home environment, student-teacher relationship, laboratory facilities, and school location.

The result of this study in table 7a, b and c revealed that there is a significant positive relationship between class size and biology students’ academic achievement in senior secondary schools of Taraba state. This finding agrees with the study of Imoke (2006) who postulated that class size implies rational coordination of educational infrastructures, subject to an available number of students to attain a high level of productivity and academically achievable. Also, Allen (2013) study has similar view with this finding, which indicated that 62 students per teacher were a threshold number and once class size goes beyond 62, learning effectively stopped. Thus, as the number of students in a class goes above 62, teachers find it difficult to teach effectively and efficiently leading to students not being able to learn effectively since low participation in class activities was not possible.

The findings of this study in Table 12a, b, and c indicated that there is a significant positive relationship between school learning environment variables combined and biology students’ academic achievement in senior secondary schools of Taraba state. The finding agreed with the study of Obong (2007) who found out that quality of learning facilities available within the school learning environment variables has a positive relationship with the quality of teaching and learning activities

which in turn predict Biology students' academic achievement. Mark (2007) and Ajayi (2007) in expressing their view maintained that a students' educational outcome and academic success are greatly predicted by the type of school that they attend. School variables include school structure (class size), school location, biology laboratories facilities, teacher-student relationship, and school climate.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of this study, it is concluded that there is a statistically significant positive relationship between class size and biology students' academic achievement in senior secondary schools, also home environment significantly makes a positive relationship between biology students' academic achievement in senior secondary schools. The finding of the study revealed that there is a statistically significant positive relationship between students-teacher relationships and biology students' academic achievement in senior secondary schools, it was found out that there is a statistically significant positive relationship between biology laboratory facilities and biology students' academic achievement in senior secondary schools. The findings indicated that school location makes a statistically significant positive prediction on biology students' academic achievement in senior secondary schools. It was also concluded that school learning environment variables such as class size, home environment, student-teacher relationship, biology laboratory facilities, and school location make a statistically significant positive prediction on biology students' academic achievement in senior secondary schools of Taraba state.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. It is recommended that biology teachers in senior secondary schools should ensure that the recommended class size of 35-50 stated in the National Policy of Education is maintained to ensure good teacher – students contact during classroom lesson.
2. Parents should make sure that the home environment is conducive for students after school hours to allow students to study well in quiet and safe environment. Such can improve their academic achievement.
3. The school authority (principals) should ensure that teachers and students relate well so as to enhance students' academic achievement.
4. Government, non-governmental organizations and school authorities should ensure that laboratory facilities are available and effectively utilized by the teachers.
5. Government, educators, and school principals should make sure that a school is located at the appropriate place where students can study without distraction. School should be located where noise level is low, with proper structure, and well-equipped laboratory.
6. Government, parents, teachers, and school principals should ensure that school learning environment variables such as class size, home environment, students-teachers relationship, biology laboratory facilities, and school location are given more attention for better academic achievement of students.

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